

BioWood

D1.2: Selection of existing forest/stand growth models
relevant for Flanders

**Ilié Storms, Pieterjan De Geest, Jos Van Orshoven,
Bruno Verbist, Bart Muys**

Study accomplished in the framework of the
FWO SBO project S003518N Report No.
S003518N_WP1D2

October 2020

Content

Introduction	5
1 Forest/stand growth models used in Sim4Tree.....	7
2 Improving the yield tables of Sim4Tree.....	7
2.1 <i>Effects of growth curve selection on biomass growth</i>	<i>7</i>
2.2 <i>Effects on site index</i>	<i>8</i>
2.3 <i>Effects on maximal considered stand age.....</i>	<i>8</i>
3 Model selection for improving yield table utilization under climate change..	15
4 Summary.....	17
5 Acknowledgements	18
6 References.....	19

Introduction

The bio-economy encompasses the use of renewable bio-resources such as wood, and their conversion into products, biofuels, feed and food via biorefinery technologies. Bio-based industries are a significant subsector of the bio-economy, and a strong bio-based industrial sector helps to reduce society's dependency on fossil-based products. Nevertheless a single Flemish, let alone European, bio-based industry sector does not exist. Rather a wide range of different sectors work in isolation. This lack of value chains and the missing support for their development hampers growth of the biobased industry in Flanders and the EU.

The primary aim of the BioWood research project is to scientifically support the development of a wood-based value chain in Flanders. Reaching this goal relies on the integration of a sustainable wood supply, feasible conversion processes and unique high-value bio-based products. To that end, a major scientific challenge related to woody biomass supply is the development of a reliable methodology for calculating its current and future availability in Flanders.

A recently developed information and decision support system (DSS) Sim4Tree (Dalemans et al., 2015) can serve as a basis for tackling this challenge but is, in its current state, unable to account for the uncertainty related to projecting future biomass availability. Updating the system with (i) more recent yield tables and (ii) land-cover maps, (iii) ecological and technical restrictions for biomass harvesting, (iv) scaling factors accounting for productivity changes due to climate change and (v) inclusion of different land-use scenarios are necessary to make more accurate predictions on biomass availability.

The goal of this deliverable is to update the current forest/stand growth models used in Sim4Tree with (i) more recent models to improve the accuracy of our predictions of biomass availability as well as (ii) to select a model to improve the useability of the empirical yield tables under climate change.

1 Forest/stand growth models used in Sim4Tree

Input for the Sim4Tree tool applied to Flanders consists of a grid of one-hectare pixels each containing information on the presence or absence of forest. Forest pixels contain additional information on the stand, i.e. species, age and site index. The site index reflects the productivity of a stand for a given tree species. In Flanders, which is a small and relatively plain region, this site index is not much determined by climate, but primarily by soil texture and soil water regime. The productivity of the stands are characterised by yield tables originating from the Netherlands (Jansen et al., 1996). These yield tables describe forest growth over time for homogeneous mono-species even-aged stands and are derived from historical measurements obtained in the national forest inventory, in permanent sampling plots and experimental plots. The yield tables make provision for different site indices and thinning intensities.

The current base map in Sim4Tree reflects the state of the forest pixels in 2010 as derived from the forest map developed in 2000 combined with intermediate results of the Flemish forest inventory (Agentschap Natuur en Bos, 2019). To each pixel of the base map containing the information about the stands in 2010 the site index is assigned as derived from the Belgian soil map (cartographic source scale 1:20.000). Hence every pixel is coupled to the correct yield table.

2 Improving the yield tables of Sim4Tree

The yield tables of Jansen (1996) currently used in Sim4Tree have been updated in 2018 by Wageningen University & Research (Jansen & Oosterbaan, 2018) and adjusted to better fit the forest management in Flanders (H. Jansen et al., 2020). This updated version has now been incorporated in Sim4Tree and was the result foremost of improved statistical analyses, of the inclusion of additional growth observations and extension of rotation times. For each species a more extensive set of empirical growth curves (Chapman-Richards, Burkhardt & Tennent, Jansen & Hildebrand, Jansen or Cieszewski) were considered and for some species, the number of site classes changed. For the Flemish yield tables, the maximum age considered in the yield tables was extrapolated.

2.1 Effects of growth curve selection on biomass growth

With the new growth curves considered in the 2018 version of the yield tables it was possible to describe the growth pattern of the considered species more accurately. Apart from the Chapman-Richards equation (Richards, 1959), the heteromorph Burkhardt & Tennent model (Burkhardt & Tennent, 1977), Jansen & Hildebrand (J. J. Jansen & Hildebrand, 1986), Jansen (J. J. Jansen et al., 1996) and Cieszewski (Cieszewski, 2001) model were considered. As candidate growth curves for each species, the most optimal model was selected based on a multi-criteria analysis considering different statistical parameters. The models selected for each species can be found in Table 1.

2.2 Effects on site index

The change in the number of site classes meant that for some species, the new site classes had to be linked to different soil types in Flanders (Table 1). Soil types were linked to site classes through the BoBo expert system, developed by INBO (De Vos, 2000). If more than five site classes were present, the five most optimal growth curves were considered, as conditions in Flanders are generally better than site conditions in the Netherlands (H. Jansen et al., 2020).

2.3 Effects on maximal considered stand age

In the original yield tables of 1996, the growth of species was often limited to a certain age, as beyond that age no growth measurements were available at the time of compiling the tables. Since then, the sampling plots grew older, and so did the trees, allowing to model growth beyond the previously stated maximal age. In addition, the inclusion of older stands allowed to estimate the maximal attainable height per site index more accurately. Stand growth through time shows a typical sigmoidal pattern and correct estimation of the uppermost horizontal asymptote value is key to correctly modelling the stand development and assessing the site index. Finally the yield tables were extrapolated beyond the rotation times present in the Netherlands to better match the forest management of Flanders (H. Jansen et al., 2020).

Based on the improvements described above, the changes in the new yield tables (2018) in relation to the tables of 1996 can be qualified as following:

- New species (NS)
- Species showing similar growth patterns (SG)
- Species showing differences in the growth curve (DGC)
- Species showing differences in the range of growth (both decreased and increased growth for different site indices) (DRG)
- Species showing decreased growth (DG)
- Species showing increased growth (IG)

Each species present in the yield table was assigned to one of these qualifiers (Table 1). The effect of the growth change on biomass predictions in Flanders using Sim4Tree is shown for each species in Figure 1-4.

Table 1: Summary of the most significant changes in the revised empirical yield tables of 2018 compared to the original version of 1996. Categories correspond to growth changes: similar growth patterns (SG), difference in range of growth (DRG), difference in growth curve (DGC), decreased growth (DG), increase in growth (IG) and new species (NS). Thinning regimes are divided into moderate thinning (MT), heavy thinning (HT) and alternative thinning (AT) – corresponding to thinning regimes different from MT and HT.

Species	Change qualifier	Year	Model height growth	Site indices	Maximum age	Thinning regimes		
						AT	MT	HT
<i>Pinus sylvestris</i>	DRG	1996	Richards, (1959)	5	100			
		2018	Cieszewski, (2001)	5	150			
<i>Pinus nigra</i> subsp <i>laricio</i>	IG	1996	Richards, (1959)	6	90			
		2018	Jansen & Hildebrand, (1986)	7	80			
<i>Pinus nigra</i> subsp <i>nigra</i>	DGC	1996	Richards, (1959)	5	100			
		2018	Jansen & Hildebrand, (1986)	7	90			
<i>Pseudotsuga menziesii</i>	IG	1996	Richards, (1959)	5	100			
		2018	Richards, (1959)	5	120			
<i>Larix kaempferi</i>	DG	1996	Richards, (1959)	5	80			
		2018	Cieszewski, (2001)	5	70			
<i>Picea abies</i>	DRG	1996	Jansen & Hildebrand, (1986)	6	80			
		2018	Cieszewski, (2001)	5	90			
<i>Quercus robur</i>	DRG	1996	Richards, (1959)	7	120			
		2018	Cieszewski, (2001)	5	150			
<i>Quercus rubra</i>	SG	1996	Richards, (1959)	7	100			
		2018	Jansen & Hildebrand, (1986)	5	100			
<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	DG	1996	Jansen et al. (1996)	5	150			
		2018	Cieszewski, (2001)	5	150			
<i>Populus cultivars</i>	DG	1996	Jansen et al. (1996)	7	45			
		2018	Gompertz, (1825); Richards, (1959)	5	50			
<i>Populus tremula</i>	NS	1996	NA	NA	NA	NA		
		2018	Gompertz, (1825); Richards, (1959)	5	55			
<i>Betula pendula</i>	DG	1996	Richards, (1959)	4	90			
		2018	Cieszewski, (2001)	5	80			
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	IG	1996	Richards, (1959)	6	90			
		2018	Cieszewski, (2001)	5	90			
<i>Alnus glutinosa</i>	IG	1996	Mitscherlich, (1945)	5	90			
		2018	Jansen et al. (2016)	5	60			
<i>Acer pseudoplatanus</i>	NS	1996	(J. J. Jansen et al., 1996)(J. J. Jansen et al., 1996)	NA	NA	NA		

			1996)(J. J. Jansen et al., 1996)(J. J. Jansen et al., 1996)NA					
	2018		Cieszewski, (2001)	5	80			

Figure 1: Evolution of total harvest (top) and standing stock (bottom) in Flanders for *Fagus sylvatica* (right), *Quercus rubra* (middle) and *Quercus robur* (left) according to the yield tables from 1996 (black) and the revised version from 2018 (red)

Figure 2: Evolution of total harvest (top) and standing stock (bottom) in Flanders for *Fraxinus excelsior* (right), *Pseudotsuga menziesii* (middle) and *Pinus nigra subsp. laricio* (left) according to the yield tables from 1996 (black) and the revised version from 2018 (red) for the whole regions of Flanders starting from 2010 and simulated until 2200 using Sim4Tree

Figure 3: Evolution of total harvest (top) and standing stock (bottom) in Flanders for *Larix kaempferi* (right), *Betula pendula* (middle) and *Populus spp.* (left) according to the yield tables from 1996 (black) and the revised version from 2018 (red) for the whole regions of Flanders starting from 2010 and simulated until 2200 using Sim4Tree

Figure 4: Evolution of total harvest (top) and standing stock (bottom) in Flanders for *Pinus sylvestris* (right) and *Picea abies* (left) according to the yield tables from 1996 (black) and the revised version from 2018 (red) for the whole regions of Flanders starting from 2010 and simulated until 2200 using Sim4Tree

3 Model selection for improving yield table utilization under climate change

Apart from improving the predictive capacities of stand growth for current conditions by Sim4Tree, its capacities to predict growth under future conditions had to be considered as well. Climate change has been predicted to have varying effects on stand growth. Most studies predict an increase in growth in the near future through increase of CO₂ concentration and temperature changes in precipitation regimes and in nitrogen deposition. In this study, we considered the former three factors, which are well studied, while future nitrogen deposition conditions remain uncertain.

The effects of environmental conditions on forest growth are typically evaluated using mechanistic forest growth models as these models describe growth based on mathematical formulations of eco-physiological processes. A wide array of mechanistic forest growth models has been developed over time, all created to suite different research questions in varying environments. Hence, it is key to select the model best fitting the research goal or application.

We defined a number of selection criteria to evaluate the models' capacity to describe growth changes in Flemish conditions and ease of implementation in the yield tables. These criteria were defined in seven groups according to Fontes et al., (2011):

1. Scale: *Model must describe forest at a stand or landscape scale.*
2. Timestep: *The model must be able to describe changes in environmental variables at daily steps to account for the increased variability in daily temperature and precipitation extremes*
3. Simulation period: *The model must describe at least one full rotation cycle*
4. Silvicultural applications: *The model must enable the simulation of different thinning regimes*
5. Harvesting system: *The model must be able to consider clearcutting systems*
6. Forest type: *The model must be capable to deal with homogenous even-aged stands*
7. Model output: *The model must calculate mean annual increment, basal area, diameter at breast height, stand height and net primary production.*

Based on these criteria, six models were chosen for further evaluation: 3-PG (Landsberg & Waring, 1997), LandClim (Schumacher et al., 2004), 4C (Lasch-Born et al., 2020), Landis-II (Scheller & Mladenoff, 2004), PICUS (Lexer & Hönninger, 2001) and BIOME-BGC (White et al., 2000). The second evaluation considered the species present in the model and the countries where the model had been successfully applied already. BIOME-BGC was excluded from this further selection, as it did not describe the most prominent species in Flanders (Figure 5), while LANDIS-II was excluded since it was never used in regions close to Flanders. Finally, the models were evaluated on their capacity to deal with complex soil conditions as the soil is one of the major factors determining growth variations in Flanders. 4C had the most complex soil module, a multi-layered bucket model, for which all input variables were available for Flanders at an acceptable resolution, and was

therefore selected as the model of preference to calculate the effect of future environmental conditions on forest growth.

Figure 5: (a) Species proportion by area for the Flemish region, (b) total area of species coverage for publicly and privately owned forests. Species groupings were taken according to definitions given in Alderweireld et al. (2015) with the exception of an additional category “Betula spp.”, which was defined as a stand with at least 2/3 of the total basal area covered by Betula spp. “Douglas” was removed due to its small share (<1%) (adapted from Storms & Muys, 2020).

The process-based forest growth model 4C (‘FORESEE’ –FORESt Ecosystems in a changing Environment) (Lasch-Born et al., 2020) describes tree growth processes based on physiological modelling, long-term growth observations and eco-physiological experiments considering carbon, water and nutrient fluxes. The model requires daily meteorological data, average stand characteristics and chemical and physical soil characteristics for each soil horizon up to 1 m depth. A detailed description of the model can be found in Lasch-Born et al. (2015). The model has been used and validated to evaluate forest growth responses to climate in Germany (Lasch-Born et al., 2015), Belgium (Kint et al., 2009), Finland (Mäkelä et al., 2000), Russia (Suckow et al., 2016) and Europe (Reyer et al., 2014; Schelhaas et al., 2015).

4 Summary

Two models were selected to improve the forest growth module of the Sim4Tree information and decision support system. First, the yield tables (published in 1996) originally used in Sim4Tree were updated with the revised version of these tables for Flanders (H. Jansen et al., 2020). This improvement allowed for the inclusion of new species, different thinning regimes and longer rotation periods. They are based on a wider variety of growth curve models to handle the empirical growth measurement data obtained in forest stands in the Netherlands. Second, a model was selected that can model growth taking into account changing environmental conditions. An initial screening reduced the number of possible growth models to six, which were then evaluated in terms of (1) their applicability in Flanders or neighboring regions and (2) their capacity to handle the most important species in Flanders. The forest growth model 4C was finally selected due to reported experience with its use in Flanders, its capability to model growth of the prominent species occurring in Flanders' forests and its capability to deal with a wide range of soil types.

5 Acknowledgements

We acknowledge funding by the FWO SBO project 'Biowood'. I.S. holds a SB-doctoral fellowship of the Research Foundation Flanders (FWO).

6 References

- Agentschap Natuur en Bos, 2019. Vlaamse Bosinventarisatie database
- Alderweireld, M., Burnay, F., Pitchugin, M., & Lecomte, H. (2015). *Inventaire forestier wallon*. http://iprfw.spw.wallonie.be/docs/Publication_Inventaire-forestier-wallon.pdf
- Burkhardt, H. E., & Tennent, R. B. (1977). Site index equations for radiata pine in New Zealand. *New Zealand Journal Forestry Science*.
- Cieszewski, C. J. (2001). Three methods of deriving advanced dynamic site equations demonstrated on inland Douglas-fir site curves. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1139/x00-132>
- Dalemans, F., Jacxsens, P., Van Orshoven, J., Kint, V., Moonen, P., & Muys, B. (2015). Assisting sustainable forest management and forest policy planning with the sim4tree decision support system. *Forests*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f6040859>
- De Vos, B. (2000). *BOBO versie 1.0 - Bodemgeschiktheid voor bomen?*
- Fontes, L., Bontemps, J.-D., Bugmann, H., Van Oijen, M., Gracia, C., Kramer, K., Lindner, M., Rötzer, T., & Skovsgaard, J. P. (2010). Models for supporting forest management in a changing environment. *Forest Systems*, 19, 8–29. <https://doi.org/10.5424/fs/201019s-9315>
- Gompertz, B. (1825). On the nature of the function expressive of the law of human mortality, and on a new mode of determining the value of life contingencies. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London*.
- Jansen, H., De Geest, P., Storms, I., & Muys, B. (2020). *Opbrengsttabellen Vlaanderen 2020*.
- Jansen, H., & Oosterbaan, A. (2018). Opbrengsttabellen Nederland 2018. In *Opbrengsttabellen Nederland 2018*. <https://doi.org/10.3920/978-90-8686-876-6>
- Jansen, J. J., & Hildebrand, J. W. (1986). *Een nieuwe opbrengsttabel voor de fijnspar (Picea abies Karst.) in Nederland*.
- Jansen, J. J., Schoonderwoerd, H., Mohren, G. J. M., & den Ouden, J. (2016). *Groei en productie van douglas in Nederland*.
- Jansen, J. J., Sevenster, J., & Faber, P. J. (1996). *Opbrengsttabellen voor belangrijke boomsoorten in Nederland. IBN rapport 221. 6888(221)*.
- Kint, V., Lasch, P., Lindner, M., & Muys, B. (2009). Multipurpose conversion management of Scots pine towards mixed oak-birch stands-A long-term simulation approach. *Forest Ecology and Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2008.08.031>
- Landsberg, J. J., & Waring, R. H. (1997). A generalised model of forest productivity using simplified concepts of radiation-use efficiency, carbon balance and partitioning. *Forest Ecology and Management*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127\(97\)00026-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127(97)00026-1)
- Lasch-Born, P., Suckow, F., Gutsch, M., Reyer, C., Hauf, Y., Murawski, A., & Pilz, T. (2015). Forests under climate change: Potential risks and opportunities. *Meteorologische Zeitschrift*. <https://doi.org/10.1127/metz/2014/0526>

- Lasch-Born, P., Suckow, F., Reyer, C. P. O., Gutsch, M., Kollas, C., Badeck, F. W., Bugmann, H. K. M., Grote, R., Fürstenau, C., Lindner, M., & Schaber, J. (2020). Description and evaluation of the process-based forest model 4C v2.2 at four European forest sites. *Geoscientific Model Development*. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-13-5311-2020>
- Lexer, M. J., & Hönninger, K. (2001). A modified 3D-patch model for spatially explicit simulation of vegetation composition in heterogeneous landscapes. *Forest Ecology and Management*. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127\(00\)00386-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127(00)00386-8)
- Mäkelä, A., Sievänen, R., Lindner, M., & Lasch, P. (2000). Application of volume growth and survival graphs in the evaluation of four process-based forest growth models. *Tree Physiology*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/treephys/20.5-6.347>
- Mitscherlich, G. (1945). Schwarzerlen-Ertragstafel. In *Ertragstafeln wichtiger Baumarten*.
- Reyer, C. P. O., Lasch-Born, P., Suckow, F., Gutsch, M., Murawski, A., & Pilz, T. (2014). Projections of regional changes in forest net primary productivity for different tree species in Europe driven by climate change and carbon dioxide. *Annals of Forest Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13595-013-0306-8>
- Richards, F. J. (1959). A flexible growth function for empirical use. *Journal of Experimental Botany*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/10.2.290>
- Schelhaas, M. J., Nabuurs, G. J., Hengeveld, G., Reyer, C., Hanewinkel, M., Zimmermann, N. E., & Cullmann, D. (2015). Alternative forest management strategies to account for climate change-induced productivity and species suitability changes in Europe. *Regional Environmental Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-015-0788-z>
- Scheller, R. M., & Mladenoff, D. J. (2004). A forest growth and biomass module for a landscape simulation model, LANDIS: Design, validation, and application. *Ecological Modelling*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2004.01.022>
- Schumacher, S., Bugmann, H., & Mladenoff, D. J. (2004). Improving the formulation of tree growth and succession in a spatially explicit landscape model. *Ecological Modelling*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2003.12.055>
- Storms, I., & Muys, B. (n.d.). Belgium. In *Atlas of forest management in Europe*.
- Suckow, F., Lasch-Born, P., Gerstengarbe, F. W., Werner, P. C., & Reyer, C. P. O. (2016). Climate change impacts on a pine stand in Central Siberia. *Regional Environmental Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-015-0915-x>
- White, M. A., Thornton, P. E., Running, S. W., & Nemani, R. R. (2000). Parameterization and Sensitivity Analysis of the BIOME-BGC Terrestrial Ecosystem Model: Net Primary Production Controls. *Earth Interactions*. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1087-3562\(2000\)004<0003:pasoot>2.0.co;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1087-3562(2000)004<0003:pasoot>2.0.co;2)

DEPARTEMENT EARTH AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES
Celestijnenlaan 200E bus 2411
3001 LEUVEN, België
phone + 32 16 32 97 26
fax + 32 16 3 29760
bart.muys@kuleuven.be
Error! Hyperlink reference not valid.

